

Paper 16

STUDENT ENRICHMENT INITIATIVES FOR HIGHER EDUCATION

Harinakshi¹, Pradeep M. D.² & Mithun Chandra R. K.³

¹Faculty, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email: harinakshisuvarna02@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

³Faculty, Department of Business Management, University Evening College, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India Email: mithoonchandra008@gmail.com

Abstract

Education plays a great role in our life. It is an important medium of acquiring knowledge. Today knowledge is power and society accept that people with more knowledge is more empowered. India was known in the world for its few oldest Universities including Thakshashila University, Nalanda University and Ujjaini University etc. India is considered to be the hub of higher education after US and China. Higher education is a level of education obtained by students after completing secondary education. Since the globalization, industrialization and advancement of Information Technology, the Higher Education System of many countries experienced several changes during the last few decades. Preparing students to face competitive world has become a challenge to the teachers. Along with the knowledge gained from books, teachers need to train students with live examples. Various strategies such as presentation, group discussion, industrial visit, etc. are added to the curriculum. Students are allowed to have contact with the external world. The traditional teaching method of chalk and talk is replaced by other methods to learn and experience the outer world to enrich their knowledge. Bringing changes based on the present requirement is the need of the time.

Keywords: University, Higher Education, Changes, Knowledge, Teaching Methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

Teacher in higher education helps to develop student's way of thinking, behaviour and approach towards their field of study and practice. Student's performance gets affect by various factors including pedagogy used for teaching, student's self-discipline, teaching environment, resources available, etc. This study aims to study methods adopted by the teachers of higher education in order to suggest strategies to improve the overall performance of the students. The innovative pedagogies will certainly improve the quality of educational system of the country. This study is done through conducting extensive literature review upon various journals, texts, articles, websites, blogs etc.

2. PEDAGOGIES USED IN HIGHER EDUCATION

(a) Pedagogies for Effective Teaching: Lecture is the primary method of teaching which could even be supported with interactive sessions by conducting group discussion. The

lecture cum demonstration method can be performed through role play, brain storming, case studies, case presentation, games, field application etc. Student Centric Teaching Method has shifted the focus from teacher to students in the education system. By giving autonomy to students, the traditional method of teacher centric teaching practice was eliminated[1]. The learner centric classrooms operates by providing Smart Classrooms, projector based teaching, audio visual aids etc [2]. Guest Lecture delivered by eminent academic and industrial experts provides opportunity for the students to interact with such experts to provide insights to understand leadership roles, team work, interpersonal skills and right attitude to chase success. Soft Skill Training will provide competitive edge to distinguish them from other candidates with similar qualification. Remedial classes are conducted to revise the curriculum at the end of semesters will help the slow learners in the class to perform better in the semester examination. Special classes can be conducted for the slow learners to bring them to the mainstream by improving their learning speed. One to One teaching pedagogy allows communication and feedback based on the learners needs with undivided attention.

(b) Pedagogies for Effective Learning: The differing learning abilities of students are taken into consideration during the teaching learning processes [3]. Learner Centric Approach along with Information Communication Technology enabled methodologies are adopted to equip learners to compete with the tech-savvy environment [4]. This up gradation has increased the speed of learning. Technology has improved the speed of learning process through the internet [5]. Technology based learning stimulates younger generation to learn skills in the light of global competition existing in the employment market. Participatory approach encourages active student participation in the learning process [6]. Participant will become active learner rather than a passive receiver of information. These approaches provide deeper knowledge and enhance their learning skills. Students are encouraged to participate in the tasks of speaking, listening, writing, argument, performing, countering with other students [7]. Experimental learning with “do it and learn policy” provides learning through first-hand experience. It includes the provision for fellowships to provide financial aids to support their life during the period of study. Field work permits the students to practically apply the theoretical knowledge in the field of study. Internship exposes the students into the work culture, employee relations, leadership traits, organisational profile etc. Attending workshops provides specific knowledge on a particular theme. Group Discussion encourages active participation [8] through exchanging ideas. It improves student presentation and listening aptitudes [9]. Class room presentation enrich confidence and communication.

(c) Supplementary Enrichment Programmes: Higher education Institutions are offering ‘Earn while Learn’ Programmes to support financial backward students with part time employment and saving to enriching their personal expertise for final placement. The technology based Massive Open Online Courses provided through EPG Patshala, NPTEL, SWAYAM, Edx etc. provides ample opportunity to explore blended learning with diversified courses. Industry visit will deliver understanding on the practical working environment among the student community. Project Works are assigned in the last semester trains students to identify the problem exist in the real world and find the solution for the same. Case Studies performed under the guidance of faculties will build analytical and conceptual skills among students. Extra Curricular Activities helps to develop physical, intellectual and social habits among the students. It includes participation in sports, cultural, games, art, social services activities. Classes on Yoga will them in knowing and regulating self by balancing body and mind by improving concentration thereby boosting their performance. Motivation Sessions on setting goal, self esteem, grooming and personality development will create greater

impact. Providing printed study materials will help in boosting performance of students in the examinations. Customised assignments with specified marks for internal assessment will give internal urge in searching more relevant information and present with content. College fest permits the student to showcase Team work, Management, Leadership and interactive abilities. The institutions are providing placement assistance, certificate courses, mock interviews, campus drives etc. Constitution of incubation Centres in the Campus will encourage students and staffs to take up minor and major research projects benefitting the Society.

(d) Pedagogies for Evaluation System: Learning environment provides relevant content, clear learning goals and feedback, opportunities to build social skills and strategies to help students succeed [10]. Student counselling and Mentoring Services provides opportunity for the students to share their problems to seek guidance to overcome it. Receiving feedbacks from all stakeholders enable the higher education institutions to study their strength and weaknesses to further improve the system [11]. The family members of the students should actively engage in the orientation, evaluation and grievance handling tasks of their ward by meeting the faculties occasionally. National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) insisted on framing Internal Quality Assurance Cell to maintain quality and standard in education. The grievance related to employer, employee and students shall be redressed through formal mechanisms.

(e) Administrative Pedagogies: Government initiatives on new educational policies, employment guarantee programmes, skill development projects, scholarships, fellowships, research, vocational courses plays a vital role in improving the education system. Development of Educational infrastructure including classrooms, laboratories, play ground, sports and games equipment, sanitation are crucial elements to improve student admission ratio. The New Education Policy, regulatory mechanisms of University Grants Commission (UGC), All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE), Professional Councils, National Board of Accreditation (NBA), National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) will influence the quality of higher education [12]. Financial grants by the government and University Grants Commission will improve the quality of education. The Management of Higher Education should always develop and preserve their Intellectual Property through publication of books, journals, magazines, patents, trademarks etc.

3. CONCLUSION

The education sector significantly affects the economic, social, political system of the country. Higher education is the crucial player in building India to be a super power in the World. Higher education essentially imparts knowledge, values and skills facilitating growth and productivity in the nation. Modern world caused higher education system into varied challenges. Teaching, Learning, Evaluation and administrative initiatives will build quality in education. Any innovative strategy adopted by the higher education institutions shall add value to the educational system by providing avenues for further exploration for good.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] Elvis Munyaradzi Ganyaupfu (2013) 'Teaching Methods and Students Academic Performance', *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2(9), September. 2013, 29-35.
- [2] Pradeep MD, Aithal P.S. (2015) 'Learning Through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy- An Effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Social Work Higher Education

Training, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 2(9), September, 265-270.

[3] Regina A. Garcia and Lilac A. Al-Safadi (2014) 'Intervention Strategies for the Improvement of Students Academic Performance in Data Structure Course, *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 4(5), October.

[4] NandkishorSoni,Teerath Prasad Patel (2014) 'Quality Teaching & Higher Education System in India', *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4(1), January

[5] County, Kenya, Joel Silla Muema, David M. Mulwa, Stephen N. Mailu. (2018). 'Relationship Between Teaching Method And Students Performance In Mathematics In Public Secondary Schools In Dadaab Sub County, Garissa', *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 8(5) September–October, 59-63

[6] Ram Tirath. (2017). 'A study of Innovative Teaching Methods for State of the Art Education in India', *International Journal of Business Administration and Management*, 7(1).

[7] Pooja Gupta (2017). 'Study the effect of teaching method on the academic achievement of school going children of Semiurban Area, Secondary Schools of Lucknow city, *International Journal of Home Science*, 3(2), 447-453.

[8] LI Jua, C S Canada (2014). 'Study on the Group Discussion based English Reading Teaching, *Higher Education of Social Science*, 7(1), pp. 102-106

[9] Nahid Shirani Bidabadi, Ahmmadreza Nasr Isfahani, Amir Rouhollahi, Roya Khalili. (2016). 'Effective teaching methods in higher education: requirements and barriers', *Journal of Advances in Medical Education & Professionalism*, 4(4), October, 170-178.

[10] Pradeep M.D. & Ravindra B.K. (2017). 'Pedagogies to Improve Teaching, Learning and Evaluation in Higher Education, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 2(2), 21-26.

[11] Pradeep M.D. & Kalicharan M.L. (2019). 'Feedback Management System with reference to Institutions of Higher Education: Opportunities & Challenges - An Exploratory Study, *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 4(1), March, 26-37.

[12] Akash Yadav, Sheetal Makwana & Dinesh Kumar Jain (2016). 'Regulatory Bodies of Education in India- A Review, *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 3(3), 112-119.